

Moving from Unmanaged to Managed Data

An implementation project for the Institutional Underpinnings Program

Project summary report

University of Queensland

February 2023

About the Institutional Underpinnings Program

In partnership with 25 Australian universities, we created a jointly-agreed Research Data Management Framework for Institutions for the management, sharing, retention and disposal of research data. Each partner university conducted projects to validate and test an aspect of the framework in their local contexts. This is a report on one of the projects.

More information

View more outputs of the [Institutional Underpinnings program](#).

View the [Research Data Management Framework for Institutions](#).

Project Summary

This project contributes to the Active Data Management framework element of [Research Data Management for Institutions Framework](#). Specifically, the project will produce a white paper that discusses how the University of Queensland (UQ) is providing data infrastructure that facilitates the transition from “unmanaged” data sets to “managed” ones. While this is not a perfect alignment with Active Data Management, it does contribute to a number of the recommendations, namely “Research Data Governance”, “User focused design” and “Integration for a Seamless User Experience”.

UQ has implemented a rich data fabric (MeDiCI) that provides access to research data – anywhere, anytime. This means data can be generated on scientific instruments (the dominant source of data by volume), ingested into the fabric and delivered to a wide range of computing systems (including high performance clusters). MeDiCI takes charge of automatic data movement and manages data migration across a variety of storage structures of varying cost and performance. Ultimately data is moved to inexpensive “cold” storage for long term preservation. Collection level meta-data is managed by the University Research Data Manager (RDM) system, a Web based portal that maintains high level meta-data about each collection.

Importantly, MeDiCI and the associated infrastructure hold “unmanaged” data. We are currently implementing a number of high-level data repositories on top of MeDiCI to support “managed” data collections, specifically those gathered from scientific instruments. These repositories, such as XNAT, OMERO, myTARDIS and Clowder establish a database that records meta-data extracted from the instruments. This makes it possible to organise data based on the meta-data rather than files.

In this project we will describe how both managed and unmanaged data can co-exist in MeDiCI, and how it is possible to migrate from unmanaged to managed and back. Specifically, the Clowder repository can ingest and index previously unmanaged data and present it through a set of Web interfaces. Importantly, data can still be presented as unmanaged collections and processed on a variety of computer systems – including HPC clusters.

Resulting Improvements

Prior to this project UQ already had an operational RDM, and this underpins all storage requests going forward. RDM is critical for robust management of our data assets, and supports a wide range of policy decisions going forward. RDM maintains a centralised list of data collection owners and keeps at least minimal metadata such as FOR codes for the data.

We have augmented our UQRDM (Research Data Manager) so that collections can be either unmanaged or managed. Unmanaged collections are structured as simple folders and can be mounted on multiple university compute resources as such (ranging from desktops to NeCTAR cloud to HPC). For these collections the RDM keeps the high level metadata. Managed collections have an additional metadata

resource attached which keeps a variety of instrument level metadata. Currently we support OMERO, XNAT and Clowder repository stacks.

Next Steps

We are rolling out multiple repositories to more instruments. The [ARDC AIS project](#) has been supporting the expansion of XNAT at the University, and the [ARDC ACCS project](#) has been supporting the expansion of the NCSA Clowder service. More instruments are added monthly. This RDM for Institutions Framework project has provided the overall framework for this work to occur.

Project Outputs

Abramson, D., Barkauskas, D., Carroll, J., Condon, N., Modhiran, N., Nguyen, H., Springfield, J. and Watterson, D., “Democratising large scale instrument-based science through e-Infrastructure”, 18th IEEE International Conference on e-Science, Salt Lake City, Utah, October 10th – 14th, 2022.

[doi:10.1109/eScience55777.2022.00033](https://doi.org/10.1109/eScience55777.2022.00033)

The work has been documented in a publicly available paper. The paper described a set of services including the repository services.

View more outputs of the [Institutional Underpinnings program](#).